

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

SWOT ANALYSIS OF GEORGIAN RESORTS

Gigi Kuparadze

Professor at Grigol Robakidze University

Abstract

The present article, “*SWOT Analysis of Georgian Resorts*,” includes a brief history of resort development in Georgia, as well as an overview of the current situation and future opportunities. Among the **Strengths**, it presents Georgia’s favorable geographical location, diverse climate, abundance of mineral and thermal waters, recognition of certain resorts (Borjomi, Tskaltubo, Gudauri, etc.), rich historical and cultural heritage, the high rate of tourism growth in the country, government support, and more. The **Weaknesses** discuss the absence of a unified national strategy for resort development, outdated infrastructure, inadequate sanitary conditions, limited diversification of the visitor market, and a shortage of qualified personnel. The excessive focus on treatment and weak marketing also remain significant challenges. The **Opportunities** relate to clustering resorts, establishing a coordination system between the public and private sectors, diversifying the tourism product, implementing measures to extend the season, involving local communities, and creating favorable conditions for investments. The **Threats** include risks of political and economic instability in the country and the region, insufficient state regulation of medical tourism, lack of protection of legislation, and threats arising from climate change, which have a particularly significant impact on resorts. Overall, the document emphasizes the need for a unified national strategy, professional development, modernization of infrastructure, and strong branding in order for Georgia to become a high-quality international resort destination.

Keywords: Georgian resorts; Resort clusters; Health tourism; Medical tourism; Wellness tourism; Balneology.

Current Situation

Georgia has a rich history of natural healing resources and resort development. Mineral waters have been used for healing since ancient times, evidenced by archaeological remains in Borjomi and Armazi baths which were supplied with healing mineral waters (Description of Monuments of History and Culture of Georgia, vol. 5, Tsitsishvili, 1990. — pp. 239-241). In the city of Dzalisi (2nd - 8th centuries BC) (Tsitsishvili Irakli, History of Georgian Art. - Tsitsishvili, 1995. - pp. 33-34; 41-43) According to the remains of communal buildings and sanitary-hygienic equipment discovered as a result of archaeological excavations, we can judge the high standard of living of the population in this era and, accordingly, a high hygienic culture. One of the proofs of this is the Tbilisi Sulfur Baths, the existence of which, according to legend, became the reason for the founding of Tbilisi in the 5th century.

However modern resort development began in the second half of the 19th century, with Borjomi, Gagra, and Abastumani frequented by the Russian royal family, where luxurious palaces and bathhouses were built at that time. In Georgia, by the decree of May 20, 1921, all medical places and resorts of the republic were nationalized. Planned resort construction began. In 1928, the Scientific Research Institute of Balneology and Physiotherapy was established under the leadership of Prof. A. Koniashvili. Since 1948, its branches have been operating in Sukhumi and Tskaltubo. In 1930, the Tbilisi Balneological Resort was founded. (Gigi Kuparadze, Niko Kvaratskhelia, Some aspects of historical connections from hydrothermal public baths to the modern spa industry, Journal of Development Studies, V3-N1 (3) – 2022, pp. 52)

During the existence of Tsarist Russia and the Soviet Union, Georgia became one of the most successful resort destinations in the USSR compared to all other countries that were part of these empires. According to the 1988 data of the Statistical Service the country had 152,000 beds. Of these, 103 thousand resort places were located in sanatoriums, boarding houses and rest houses, and 49 thousand in hotels, tourist resorts and other tourism accommodation facilities. Hosting 4.5 million tourists annually. Of these, about 2 million were vacationing at resorts. If we take into account that the average duration of resort trips was 15-24 days, it turns out that during the year up to 24-30 million bed days were occupied only at Georgian resorts. In connection with this statistic, we should also note one fact: out of 4.5 million tourists who visited Georgia in 1988, 2.5 million visited Abkhazia.

However, the collapse of the USSR, wars, and political instability of the 1990s devastated the industry and this successful era for the Georgian resort industry and resortology ended very badly. The events that took place in the 1990s (the collapse of the USSR, the civil war, the transition to a new social order), and then the Russian-Georgian war in 2008, left a negative mark on Georgia's resort and recreational economy. Due to the chaos, irreparable damage was caused to flora and fauna. Many resort buildings and structures were destroyed and demolished. The state was forced to accommodate 300 thousand people displaced from the so-called South Ossetia and Abkhazia in the best hotels, sanatoriums, boarding houses and rest homes. Thus, practically in one day, the tourist and resort infrastructure of our country was destroyed.

Today, the Georgian resort industry has emerged from this difficult situation and now it is necessary to

conduct a correct analysis of the current situation, as well as to draw up a strategy and action plan for future development and its implementation.

Therefore, I decided to conduct a SWOT analysis of Georgian resorts, as it is an excellent tool for both situation and business analysis, as well as strategic planning.

In this article, I will analyze the strengths and weaknesses, opportunities and threats that affect or will affect the development of Georgian resorts.

SWOT analysis

Strengths

- Georgia's location on the border of the subtropical zone, its territory surrounded by the Caucasus Mountains from the north and the South Georgian Mountains from the south, the Black Sea, the complex relief of the location and the wealth of various vegetation have become the reason that almost all types of climates are found on the territory of Georgia: from the humid subtropical of the Black Sea and the relatively dry plains of Eastern Georgia, to the mountainous climate of all altitude zones, which has laid the foundation for the abundance of coastal and mountain climatic resorts.

- Along with the coastal and mountain climate, the presence of almost all known types of mineral waters. According to the Georgian Institute of Balneology and Physiotherapy, the total number of springs exceeds 2000, of which more than 1700 are natural outlets, and up to 300 are boreholes; their total debit exceeds 120 million liters per day. The most common are carbonated mineral waters, the total daily flow of which reaches 60 million liters.

- According to the list approved by the resolution of the Government of Georgia, there are balneological, climatic, balneo-climatic, climatic-balneological and mud-curing 103 resorts and 168 resort areas; (Resolution of the Government of Georgia No. 428, On Approval of the List and Status of Georgian Resorts, 2014)

- In addition to health resorts, the abundance of other types of resorts (mountain-ski, seaside, lakeside, etc.) and promising resort areas;

- The presence of natural healing resources and natural-recreational resources, in some cases, their uniqueness. This primarily concerns the Tbilisi balneological resort, Tskaltubo, Sairme, Nunisi geothermal mineral waters, Borjomi and Nabeglavi drinking mineral waters, Ureki beach and magnetic sand, Akhtala healing mud, etc.

- Extensive but mostly outdated multidisciplinary (geology, hydrogeology, chemistry, medicine, etc.) documentation.

- Awareness and popularity of Georgian resorts among the population of Georgia;

- Awareness and popularity of Georgian resorts among the population of some foreign countries. First of all, this concerns the former Soviet countries. In this case, we can talk about the brand - "Georgia is a country of resorts".

- The recognition and popularity of Georgian ski resorts (Bakuriani, Gudauri, Goderdzi, Mestia) both within the country and abroad.

- The long history and experience of implementing heli-ski tours at Georgian ski resorts.

- The existence of several international airports (Tbilisi, Kutaisi, Batumi) and the construction of another one, planned in Vaziani.

- Quite high rates of tourism development, both before and after the pandemic.

- Historical, cultural and natural monuments throughout Georgia, four of which are included in the UNESCO World Heritage List (Mtskheta, Gelati, Upper Svaneti and the Wetlands of Western Georgia)

- • High-class resort hotels and spa centers in some regions (in Tbilisi, Adjara, Kakheti, Guria)

- The will of the central and local authorities to develop tourism and create tourist accommodation facilities in the regions of Georgia. This is confirmed by various incentive programs launched by the Government of Georgia (e.g. "Host in Georgia", "Enterprise Georgia", etc.).

- In 2022, the LEPL Resort Development Agency was created, which is responsible for the development of resorts in Georgia

- Rapid growth rate of the country's economy in the post-pandemic period. For example, according to the IMF, Georgia's economy grew by 10.7% per capita in 2024, ranking second in the world. (<https://businessinsider.ge/Economic>)

- Traditional Georgian hospitality and 100 years of experience in welcoming local and international visitors to Georgian resorts.

Weaknesses

- Lack of a strategy and action plan for the development of resorts agreed with the Georgian government and other stakeholders in the resort industry;

- Lack of a coordination system for the development of Georgian resorts. In many cases, the development of resorts or resort facilities proceeds chaotically.

- The presence of more or less developed resorts only along the central highways of Georgia, which connect the eastern and western, as well as the northern and southern regions of the country;

- The relatively less developed resorts have weak connections with these central highways;

- Georgia does not have a sufficient number of high-quality modern resorts. Traditionally, the term "resort" was associated with medical services, while wellness resorts are not officially recognized in this category. For example, one of the most famous and popular mountain and ski resorts, Gudauri, is not included in the list of resorts approved by the Georgian government, and there are many other such cases;

- The absence of a competitive medical or wellness tourism product that meets international standards;

- Due to the fact that the majority of Georgian resorts still focus only on treatment and medical services, they practically do not use the various recreational and entertainment resources available around them.

- Lack of various types of activities at the resorts, as well as the lack of integration of resort activities and accommodation, lack of multi-seasonal activities.
- The Georgian resort market is not diversified and visitors are mainly from neighboring countries (approximately 61%). Due to this, Georgian resorts lack a segment of high-spending visitors from developed countries. The majority of international tourists arriving in Georgia in 2023 were from neighboring countries or countries in the region, including Russia (22%), Turkey (21%), Armenia (15%), Israel (5%), and other countries (38%). (Georgian National Tourism Administration, Statistical Review of Georgian Tourism 2024, p.6);
 - Unfavorable urban environment and lack of public spaces or their poor quality in Georgian resorts.
 - Inadequate, chaotic, unsightly resort and tourist infrastructure, or its complete absence;
 - Poor or very poor sanitary and hygienic conditions in most seaside, balneological and mountain climatic resorts, as well as on beaches;
 - Poor condition of access roads, water supply, sewage and other communal infrastructure in most resorts;
 - Lack of modern legislation and taxonomy corresponding to international standards;
 - Lack of new, relevant research and data on the state of natural healing resources;
 - Lack of complete and convincing statistics on the number of visitors to resorts and their expenses;
 - Lack of any convincing research on the satisfaction of visitors to resorts;
 - Shortage or absence of staff trained according to modern international standards; The Georgian resort school was one of the most distinguished among the countries of the Soviet Union and Eastern Europe, and many prominent doctors, professors and academicians were educated in its bosom. A lot of interesting theoretical and academic knowledge has been accumulated. But, unfortunately, today this is not enough. Today in Georgia, and especially in Guria, there is an acute shortage of both top and middle-level management and medical personnel who are well versed in the principles of a market economy, have knowledge and experience in business administration, are familiar with modern spa and wellness procedures, treatment methods introduced at leading resorts in the world, etc.;
 - Lack of experience in hosting foreign tourists and lack of relevant skills, including knowledge of foreign languages. (If we do not count the Russian-speaking tourists who arrived from the Soviet Union 30-35 years ago and today, mainly a small number of vacationers from former Soviet countries);
 - Weak marketing of resorts and health tourism products in target international markets, including within the country;

Opportunities

- Cluster grouping of Georgian resorts and resort areas based on the principle of proximity and contiguity so that the development of one resort in the cluster can have a positive impact on the others.
 - Cluster grouping of Georgian resorts and resort areas based on the principle of proximity and contiguity so that the development of one resort in the cluster can have a positive impact on the others.
 - Development and approval of a coordination system between public structures related to the development of resorts, as well as between public and private entities. This system should include issues of spatial planning, development of resorts in the regions, as well as coordination with business and public-private cooperation and assistance in the implementation of resort programs. Coordination with business also includes the design of resort spaces in accordance with off-season activities.
 - Planning and implementation of measures to extend the season at resorts in cooperation with the state and private sectors; promoting the development of multi-season resorts.
 - Providing assistance to the private sector from the state in creating a health tourism product. This is natural, since the health tourism product has a special concept and is also associated with the demand for holistic and spiritual services. For this, it will be necessary to organize special trainings and courses (preferably by inviting foreign experts)
 - Creation of channels for the distribution of the health tourism product. It should be noted here that the distribution of this type of product is a rather specific issue. For example, in medical tourism, facilitators (intermediaries) play a large role (and not tour operators). In wellness tourism (especially holistic or spiritual tourism), small but specialized travel companies provide package services.
 - Currently, some Georgian resorts offer guests rural products, and some wellness resorts also offer spa treatments based on local products, e.g. Saperavi wine baths. This is precisely the new global trend that involves the inclusion of local activities in resort services. In the future, the state should encourage community-based tourism, which involves providing a rural experience to visitors. Thus, the connection of resort facilities with local economic activities will be strengthened in the resort zone. It is expected that these activities will extend to agricultural products, local cultural and historical heritage, and individual communities;
 - Preparation of investment proposals for resorts and resort areas, including the privatization of the remaining state-owned property at a symbolic price;
 - Diversification of the resort visitor market, work on new target segments in order to attract high-spending visitors. To this end, the popularization and branding of Georgia as a resort destination, as well as the promotion of individual resorts, should be strengthened. For this purpose, appropriate marketing and communication activities need to be implemented, which will be planned and discussed in close coordination with organizations related to the resort.

Threats

- Political and economic instability and risks of the country and the region. However, resort and tourism infrastructure requires quite large investments and the period for recovering the costs incurred on their implementation is quite long
- Inadequate support for health tourism by the state. The Georgian government in general and, in particular, the National Tourism Administration are working hard and well to develop the tourism industry in general, but the same cannot be said about the health tourism direction. However, without state regulations and support, it is almost impossible to develop this area, especially medical tourism.
- Lack of certification and licensing. This is a problem for the tourism and hotel industry in general, but the system of standards and quality assurance is especially important for medical and wellness tourism facilities, which in many cases is perceived as a guarantee of the quality of the services provided by them.
- Ignorance of existing legislation. First of all, we are talking about the “Sanitary Protection Zones of Resorts and Resort Areas” in accordance with the Law of Georgia;
- Climate change and its risks: intensification of erosion processes of the coastline and beaches, increase

in the frequency of extreme meteorological processes, ranging from continuous rains and floods to long-term drought periods, changes in microclimate and intensification of landslide processes, etc.

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